

Semi-supervised Teeth Segmentation: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Semi-supervised Teeth Segmentation

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

Semi-TeethSeg

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Computer-aided diagnosis tools are increasingly popular in modern dental practice, particularly for treatment planning or comprehensive prognosis evaluation. In particular, the 2D panoramic X-ray image is an efficient way for dentists to determine invisible caries, impacted teeth and supernumerary teeth among children. Additionally, the 3D dental cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) examinations are extensively utilized in orthodontics and endodontics due to their low ray dose and the capability to visualize three-dimensional structures. However, identifying teeth from panoramic X-ray images or CBCT scans and further manually annotating the teeth is time-consuming and labor-intensive. Thus, we usually cannot obtain a huge number of labeled cases, which limits the development of deep learning algorithms for segmenting teeth and automatically analyzing diseases. As a potential alternative, semi-supervised learning can explore useful information from unlabeled cases.

In this challenge, we aim to promote the development of the tooth segmentation in panoramic X-ray images. We extend the Semi-TeethSeg2023 Challenge from binary semantic settings to multi-instance and multi-class segmentation settings, with an emphasis on instance-level segmentation. Specifically, in Semi-TeethSeg2024, we will provide instance annotations for different teeth, inclusive of pertinent category information. The segmentation algorithm is expected to accurately segment 32 permanent teeth (including wisdom teeth) and 20 possible deciduous teeth in panoramic X-ray images.

In contrast to the dataset in Semi-TeethSeg2023 (6500 panoramic X-ray images and 584 CBCT scans), the dataset for Semi-TeethSeg2024 has been expanded to include 7000 panoramic X-ray images and 600 CBCT scans. To the best knowledge, this will be the largest most diverse publicly available dataset for teeth instance segmentation. In addition, based on the results in Semi-TeethSeg2023, we found that segmentation models can not achieve a good tradeoff between segmentation accuracy and efficiency. Thus, in Semi-TeethSeg2024, the challenge evaluation criteria are not limited to segmentation accuracy, but also include runtime and GPU memory consumption, providing a comprehensive assessment of segmentation efficiency.

In summary, the Semi-TeethSeg2024 challenge has three main features:

- (1) Task: this is the first challenge for teeth instance segmentation in panoramic X-ray images and CBCT scans.
- (2) Dataset: we provide the largest dataset, including 7000 2D X-ray images and 600 3D CBCT scans spanning all age groups.
- (3) Evaluation: we not only focus on segmentation accuracy but also segmentation efficiency, which are in concordance with real clinical practice and requirements.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.challenge_

Teeth instance segmentation, Panoramic X-ray image, CBCT, Efficiency, Semi-supervised learning

Year

The challenge will take place in 2024

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

Advances in Semi-Supervised Teeth Segmentation.

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

In MICCAI Semi-TeethSeg 2023, 44 teams made successful submissions during the testing phase. Thus, we estimate there will be at least 40 teams in Semi-TeethSeg 2024.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

An overview paper will be written with the organizing team's members. Each participating team who presented their method at the challenge session is allowed two co-authorships

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Assuming that MICCAI will take place in person, we need support for basic presentation equipment (e.g. projectors, computers, monitors, loud speakers, microphones), for solution presentations from the top-ranked teams.

TASK 1: Semi-supervised Teeth Segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

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Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Teeth instance segmentation, Panoramic X-ray image, CBCT, Efficiency, Semi-supervised learning

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Organizing team:

- Yaqi Wang, College of Media Engineering, Communication University of Zhejiang, China.
- Xiaodiao Chen, College of Computer Science and Technology, Hangzhou Dianzi University, Hangzhou, China.
- Hongyuan Zhang, Health Science Center, School of Biomedical Engineering, Shenzhen University, China.
- Fan Ye, College of Computer Science and Technology, Hangzhou Dianzi University, Hangzhou, China.
- Qianni Zhang, School of Electronic Engineering and Computer Science, Queen Mary University of London, United Kingdom.
- Shuai Wang, School of Mechanical, Electrical and Information Engineering, Shandong University, Weihai, China.

Clinical evaluator:

- Yifan Zhang, Hangzhou Geriatric Stomatology Hospital, Hangzhou Dental Hospital Group, Division of Advanced Prosthetic Dentistry, Tohoku University Graduate School of Dentistry, State Key Laboratory of Oral Diseases, National Clinical Research Center for Oral Diseases, West China Hospital of Stomatology, Sichuan University, China.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Yaqi Wang, College of Media Engineering, Communication University of Zhejiang, China.

Email: wangyaqi@cuz.edu.cn.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI.

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

<https://competitions.codalab.org/competitions/>

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

To be announced.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data and pre-trained models are allowed.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

Members of the organizers' institutes can participate but are not eligible for awards.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We will provide a prize (cash and certificate) for the top three teams. The exact money of cash prize is not known yet. Sponsors for the awards are currently being investigated. The details of this will be announced on our challenge homepage at a later date.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be announced publicly through a public leaderboard and each participating team will receive the model validation results after the challenge. But only the team that submits the method description paper will be eligible for the final ranking.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

An overview paper will be written with the organizing team's members. Each participating team who presented their method at the challenge session is allowed two co-authorships. The participating teams are encouraged to publish their results separately elsewhere when adhering to the data usage rules, and (if so) no embargo will be applied.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>

- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Submissions will be made via Docker container. The participating teams should upload their algorithm to the online submission system.

We will look for sponsors for computing resources. If it is not available, we will use our local hardware. It has two 8-Cores CPUs, one NVIDIA 2080Ti GPU, and 64G RAM. Only one GPU is allowed to use during inference.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will be allowed to validate their algorithm on validation set three times before a pre-defined deadline and only once on the testing set.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
 - the registration date/period
 - the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
 - the submission date(s)
 - associated workshop days (if any)
 - the release date(s) of the results
- Announcement of challenge's opening: March 15th, 2024
 - Open for registration and Training data release: March 20th, 2024
 - Deadline for validation submission: June 15th, 2024
 - Deadline for testing submission: July 15th, 2024
 - Invitation speakers: No later than September 1st, 2024
 - Announce final results: October 6th/10th, 2024

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethical approval was obtained from Medical Ethics Committee of Sichuan Provincial People's Hospital and the University of Electronic Science and Technology Hospital Research Ethics Committee.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY NC ND.

Additional comments: The data will be distributed under the license CC BY NC ND, and the challenge participants will need to commit to not disseminate the data during the challenge duration.

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made available with the training data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Top 10 teams should make their code publicly available. The remaining teams are encouraged to make their code publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

There is no explicit sponsoring/funding of the challenge, but we aim to contact technology companies with an interest in the teeth segmentation challenge.

Only organizing members of the challenge has access to the test case labels during and after the Semi-TeethSeg challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning

- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Assistance, Screening, Prognosis, CAD, Research, Surgery, Education, Prevention.

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation.

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort is patients who need treatment for common dental diseases (caries, periapical periodontitis, pulpitis), orthodontic and endodontic restorative treatment.(patients requiring orthodontic, and endodontic prosthetic treatment).

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort includes individuals with dental treatment. Panoramic X-rays are used to view overall tooth structure, accurately segment teeth, and pinpoint dental disease, and 3D Cone Beam Computed Tomography scan for patient dentition requiring orthodontic, and endodontic prosthetic treatment.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Panoramic X-ray/3D Cone Beam Computed Tomography scan

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No additional context information will be given.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional context information will be given.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Data is acquired for the intraoral cavity. For a given patient, one 2D/3D scans will be acquired covering full/part of the upper and lower jaws with teeth.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants have to submit a Docker container that can segment 32 permanent teeth (including wisdom teeth) and 20 possible deciduous teeth in a given 2D or 3D scan.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Precision, Runtime, Robustness.

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The pediatric dental data set was obtained from cases of patients who visited the Hangzhou Xiasha Dental Hospital from March to June 2023, as well as panoramic radiographs from instrument scans at the time of the visit.

All the 3D CBCT scans were acquired with a OP300, manufactured by Instrumentarium Orthopantomograph. CBCT slices were acquired in the DICOM format at the University of Electronic Science and Technology of China Hospital. All CBCT slices were scanned before dental operations, with a resolution of 266×266 pixels in the axial view. The in-plane resolution is about 0.25×0.25 mm² and the slice thickness range from 0.25 mm to 0.3 mm.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

In general, no particular protocol is defined for the panoramic dental X-rays and 3D CBCT scans.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Panoramic radiographs were obtained from the Hangzhou Downtown Dental Hospital and international public data sets, and all data do not contain personal private information. 3D CBCT scans are originally acquired in partener dental clinics located in China. All acquired clinical data are anonymized.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data are acquired by orthodontists with more than five years of professional experience. Scans were annotated by fifteen dentists. Twelve junior dentists with at least two years of experience manually marked all teeth regions.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case, in this challenge, is a single panoramic X-ray image or CBCT scan associated with a multi-class segmentation mask.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

For the 2D panoramic dataset, the total number of cases is 7000. There are 6000/200/800 cases for training, validation, and testing, respectively. The training set includes 100 cases with labels and 5900 unlabeled cases.

For the 3D CBCT images, the dataset to-be-released contains a training set of 530 cases, a validation set of 20 cases, and a test set of 50 cases. The training set includes 30 cases with labels and 500 unlabeled cases.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The challenge is designed for benchmarking semi-supervised learning methods. Thus, only a small set of cases are labeled and a large number of unlabeled cases can be used for training.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The data are from a large real-life scenarios, thus the class distribution is representative of the real-world distribution. There is no unseen teeth types in the testing set. All the testing cases will be hidden from participants and the Docker container will be used for submission.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The teeth were annotated by 15 dentists. Twelve junior dentists with at least two years of experience manually marked all teeth regions. Three senior experts with at least ten years of experience were invited to evaluate the tooth annotations.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

For 2D Panoramic images, dentists were asked to use the BASIC annotation online platform (<https://app.basic.ai/>). For 3D CBCT scans, professional annotation software ITKSNAP (<http://www.itksnap.org/pmwiki/pmwiki.php>) is in charge of performing the annotations for dentists.

The annotation protocol is: For the determination of tooth categories, Dentists followed the FDI criteria to define the tooth class. For the segmentation mask labeling, we adhere to established research standards in tooth segmentation, using the periodontal ligament as the boundary to differentiate between teeth and alveolar bone. The periodontal ligament, being a soft tissue, exhibits a low gray value in panoramic X-ray images or CBCT scans, aiding dentists in delineating the precise contours of the teeth.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Twelve junior dentists first delineate tooth regions. Next, the senior dentists experts assessed the annotation quality, and marked a quality level (excellent, good, fail and poor) on each tooth annotation. "Excellent" annotations were deemed satisfactory and retained without further adjustments. "Good" annotations were

fine-tuning according to the experts' feedback. "Fair" and "Poor" annotations and their feedback were put back into the unlabelled data pool and were marked again.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No Aggregation.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No preprocessing steps are required.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Error is unavoidable in medical image segmentation. Image were annotated by 15 dentists including twelve junior dentists and three senior dentists. Since much of the annotation process is manual, there may be boundary inaccuracies in the root region. Fortunately, the quality control approach will largely reduce this source of error. Moreover, We will have a github repository to collect feedbacks from participants about possible errors that they discover in the dataset. This strategy was also used in MICCAI KiTS and FLARE Challenge.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The segmentation inference results are evaluated using Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), Normalized Surface Dice (NSD), Panoptic Quality (PQ), Identification Accuracy (IA), Running time (RT) and Area under GPU memory-time curve (GPU-area).

All metrics will be used to compute the ranking. We will release the code on how to calculate the eight performance metrics with the python3 version.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The six metrics are complementary. Specifically, Dice Similarity Coefficient is used to measure the region error. Normalized Surface Dice is used to measure the boundary error. Panoptic Quality is a comprehensive metric that

combines segmentation and detection quality assessment into a single measure. The Identification Accuracy metric is applied to assess the object-level localization (detection) performance of teeth. Running time is used to measure the inference speed. Moreover, we also include the area under the GPU utilization-time curve to measure the GPU consumption. These evaluation metrics will guide the algorithm to strike a balance between performance and efficiency.

In particular, the localization criterion is Mask IoU score localization criterion in segmentation challenge. Besides, we have implemented a greedy strategy to match reference and predicted objects.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The ranking scheme includes the following five steps:

Step 1. In order to maintain consistency with our previous challenge and assess the algorithm's performance at the image level, our evaluation framework will first initially compute two metrics, Dice and NSD, on a per-image basis to derive the algorithm's Dice (image_Dice) and NSD (image_NSD) scores at image-level.

Step 2. Next, given the challenge's focus on instance-level analysis, we also will employ a greedy algorithm to match the corresponding prediction results with the ground truth, allowing for the calculation of Dice (instance_Dice), NSD (instance_NSD), IA (instance_IA) and PQ (instance_PQ) scores at the instance level.

Step 3. Then, the evaluation will include measurements of running time (RT) and GPU consumption (GPU_area) for each algorithm.

Step 4. Take the mean of the eight metrics over the test cases, and rank separately among the teams.

Step 5. A final overall rank is given by taking the average of the four ranks. In the case of equal average rankings for two teams, they are considered tied.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

We will exclude the participants who fail to report on the whole testing set.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different dimensions. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in MICCAI BraTS Challenge.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,

- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

We will exclude the participants who fail to report on the whole testing set. Besides the statistical values such as mean, standard deviation of the metrics, we use the p-value in Wilcoxon test to assess whether the top performing/ranking algorithms are significantly better than the rest of algorithms. To measure the variability, ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The Wilcoxon test is chosen because it is non-parametric and allows us to perform the analysis with minimal hypotheses, and the bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

The further analyses will be discussed in a further publication after the challenge.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A